

Fields without a trap crop, but sprayed with cypermethrin, were the treated control. Unsprayed fields without a trap crop were the untreated control.

Plot size was 11 × 17 m. Each treatment was replicated four times.

At 65 DT, RTV incidence was significantly higher in the untreated control than in trap or insecticide-treated fields (Table 1). Relatively higher nymphal and adult GLH populations were recorded.

Yields were significantly higher in trap and insecticide-treated fields than in the untreated control (Table 2). Although yield was highest in insecticide-treated fields, the cost of cypermethrin lowered net gain. Limited insecticide use also conserves natural enemies of rice pests. □

Table 2. Value of yields with and without trap crop after deducting cost of cypermethrin^a. IRRI, May–Sep 1986.

Treatment	Area (ha)		Combined yield (t/ha)	Value of yield ^b (\$/ha)	Cypermethrin applied ^c (liters/ha)	Cost ^d (\$/ha)	Net value (\$/ha)
	Trap crop	Main crop					
2-row trap crop and main crop	0.074	0.926	4.5 a	787.50	0.592	14.21	713.29 a
3-row trap crop and main crop	0.109	0.891	4.2 a	735.00	0.872	20.93	714.07 a
4-row trap crop and main crop	0.144	0.856	4.4 a	770.00	1.152	27.65	742.35 a
Treated control	0	1.000	4.9 a	857.50	8.000	192.00	665.50 ab
Untreated control	0	1.000	3.3 b	577.50	0	0	577.50 b

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b US\$ = P20; value of rice (NFA price) = \$0.175/kg. ^c Eight applications to trap crop rows and treated control plots @ 0.05 kg ai/ha per treatment. ^d Cost of cypermethrin Jul 1986 = \$24/liter.

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Rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) effect on yield

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We evaluated thrips damage and subsequent yield in highly susceptible variety Bg 94-1. We assumed that natural thrips infestation would be uniform over all plots, if not controlled. Carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha was used in an

experiment in late Nov 1983. A second experiment used different insecticides. Damage was rated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 3–4 wk after sowing. After assessment, the plants were fully protected from other pest attacks.

In carbofuran-treated plots, thrips damage was rated as 1; in untreated

control plots, 7–9. Average grain yield in treated plots (3.34 t/ha) was significantly different from that in the untreated plots (2.34 t/ha) at 5% level of probability. Plots treated with different chemicals had a control rating of 1 for all but triazophos, which rated 5; untreated plots rated 7 (see figure). Yields varied. □

Thrips damage and rice yield under chemical control, Sri Lanka, 1983.

Influence of age of crop and time of planting on gall midge (GM) incidence

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Rice GM *Orseolia oryzivora* is a serious

pest of wet season (WS) rice at Edozhigi, an irrigated area in Nigeria. The rainy season in this area is Jun-Oct and farmers transplant in Sep.

We measured GM incidence on FARO 27 and FARO 29 in the 1985 WS on samples of 50 hills/variety, replicated 3 times. Percentage of silvershoots was calculated as the ratio

GM incidence by age of rice crop. Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1985 wet season.

Days after transplanting	Silvershoots ^a (%)		
	FARO 27	FARO 29	Mean
30	13.8 (21.6)	11.8 (17.4)	12.8
40	15.4 (22.6)	18.0 (25.1)	16.7
50	14.5 (21.7)	18.2 (25.2)	16.4
60	7.9 (16.1)	15.3 (22.9)	11.6
70	7.7 (16.0)	10.4 (18.6)	9.1
LSD (0.05)	10.2	6.7	

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed angular values, LSDs refer to them.

of number of silvershoots to tillers/50 hills at 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 d after transplanting (DT). GM incidence also was measured at 50 DT on FARO 27, FARO 29, and ITA212 transplanted 20 Aug, 25 Sep, and 25 Oct.

Early-maturing FARO 27 was more

prone to GM infestation at 30-50 DT and medium-maturing FARO 29 at 40-60 DT (see table). The later the transplanting date, the higher the GM incidence (see figure). But many local farmers avoid early planting because they grow upland crops before rice. □

Effect of planting time on GM incidence. Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1985 wet season.

Host plants for yellow rice borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* and white stem borer (WSB) *S. innotata*

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We measured YSB and WSB survival on two weed species common in ricefields. Individually caged plants of *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cynodon dactylon* were infested separately with newly emerged first-instar YSB and

WSB larvae.

On *C. rotundus*, both YSB and WSB larvae bored into the stem, fed on the inner contents, and pupated below the soil surface. Survival on *C. rotundus* was 78% for YSB and 53% for WSB.

On *C. dactylon*, the larvae scraped the inflorescence peduncle, fed a little on the inner stem contents, but failed to pupate. It could be that stem borer larvae initially feed on *C. dactylon*, then migrate to a newly transplanted rice crop. □

Walking the rice paddy for pest sampling does not affect yield

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It is necessary to walk the rice paddy to sample insect populations. We measured

the effect on yield of walking in the paddy.

Variety IR64 was transplanted 20 d after seeding at 25 × 25 cm. The field was divided into 24 plots measuring 2 × 5 m each. Four treatments (see table) were replicated six times in a

randomized complete block design.

There was no significant difference in yield. □

Effect on yield of walking through rice paddy. IRRI. 1986.

Walking (no./wk)	Yield (t/ha)
0 ^a	2.5
1	2.5
3	2.5
6	2.4

^aPlots not walked on 14-77 d after transplanting.

Occurrence of a virulent rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason biotype(?) in Andhra Pradesh, India

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During the 1986 wet season, GM severely damaged rice crops in northeastern Andhra Pradesh, where large tracts were planted to GM-resistant varieties Phalguna (RPW 6-17) and Surekha (developed from IR8/ Siam 29). These varieties were released in 1977 and 1976.

We assessed damage in cooperation with the extension staff of the Department of Agriculture, Andhra Pradesh.

Damage in Phalguna and Surekha averaged more than 50% silvershoots. Maximum damage approached 96%.

Susceptible varieties were severely damaged — CR1014, 33%; Mahsuri, 57%; RNR17, 78%; Sona, 84%; and Swarna, 88%.

Pest buildup was probably favored by high rainfall (410 mm) late Jun to mid-Aug, and frequent cyclonic storms in Sep and Oct, resulting in cloudy and humid periods. Farmers also were not familiar with control measures because GM had not occurred severely for more than 10 yr. Studies over 10 yr under the AICRIP coordinated entomology program have established 3 distinct biotypes, based on reactions to differential donors Eswarakora and